

Review Article

Herbal Cosmetics and Skin Care Formulations

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ABSTRACT

Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha, homoeopathy, and other natural herb-based health sciences (AYUSH) are being developed with an emphasis on India. The development of the saundrya prasadka category of herbal cosmetics has a lot of potential and potential in the Ayush Pharmaceutical sector. Cosmetics assist in displaying and enhancing human beauty and personality traits. Natural beauty is a blessing. The formulation known as Saundrya Prasadak is a cosmetic basis that corresponds with known Ayurvedic, Siddhanic, and Unani (ASU) medicine active ingredients (references to which are easily accessible in Schedule 1st Book of the medicine and Cosmetic Act 1940 and Rule 1945). For saundrya prasadan karma, individuals in the traditional past used a variety of lepas, including Alepas, Pralepas, Udavartans, and Prakshalans. The solution to maintain such parity has been provided by nature. Herbs indeed, one such method is using herbs. An herb is a plant or plant extract that contains parts such as leaves, bark, berries, roots, gums, seeds, stems, and flowers that are particularly high in nourishing and therapeutic components. For the skin and other body parts to be properly cared for, cosmetics alone are insufficient. In order to prevent skin aging and damage, active components must be combined. In recent years, the popularity of herbal cosmetics has grown significantly. Due to its frequent usage in daily life and lack of the negative side effects sometimes associated with synthetic cosmetics, herbal cosmetics were said to be effective and intrinsically acceptable.

INTRODUCTION

The term "natural cosmetics" also applies to herbal cosmetics. Because they have no negative side effects, herbal treatments are becoming more and more popular [1]. Humankind took the alluring step toward impressing others with their appearance when civilization began. There were

no expensive fairness creams or cosmetic procedures available at the time. The only data they had at first was that gathered from nature in the Ayurveda. A few herbs and plants were used in the art of Ayurveda to create effective ayurvedic cosmetics. Ayurvedic cosmetics protected the body from external influences of any type in

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addition to beautifying the skin. Herbal cosmetics, another name for ayurvedic cosmetics, to have excellent resources available today. Medicinal plants, minerals, and organic matter are the source of many traditional medicines currently in use [2]. Herbal cosmetics are developed in a wide range and are frequently used for daily reasons. The general public has a particularly high regard for herbal cosmetics such herbal conditioner, herbal soaps, herbal face wash, herbal shampoo, and many more. The fact that herbal cosmetics are solely created from herbs and shrubs is their strongest feature. The natural components of the herbs have no effects on the human body; instead, they strengthen it with vitamins and other beneficial minerals. Herbal cosmetics are made of plants like saffron (kesar), ashwagandha, sandalwood (chandan), and many more that are grown with good nutrition and all the other necessary ingredients. Even though only around 70 spices are recognized officially, it is estimated that about 400 tastes are used widely. Herbs are used in a wide range of products, including tea, tablets, capsules, tinctures, creams, syrups, and liquids for medical, cosmetics, and food flavoring. As a result of rising demand for ethnic foods, natural perfumes, and innovative beverage products, the global herbal business is currently estimated to be worth over US\$10 billion and growing at a pace of three to four percent yearly. Europe and Asia are the two largest markets in terms of production and consumption.

Herbal products have uses in cosmetics

The world of cosmetics benefits greatly from the use of herbs [3,4].

i) Herbal Skin Care Products: Lavender body powder and body soap, Silk Soaps and Care Creams.

ii) Herbal Hair Care Cosmetics: Herbal hair care cosmetics have a several ingredient e.g Shikakai (*Acacia concinna*), Henna (*Lawsonia inermis*),

Guar Gum (*Cyamopsis tetragonolobus*) Amla (*Emblca officinalis*), Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*).

iii) Herbal Lip Care Cosmetics: Herbal Lip plumper, Herbal Lipsticks, Herbal Lip Balm and Herbal Lip Gloss.

iv) Herbal Eye Care Cosmetics: Eye Shadow, Eye Gloss, Eye Make Up, Liquid Eye Liners

v) Herbal Creams, Lotions, Gel: Creams: Rich Face and Hand Cream, Aloe Moisturizing Hand

vi) Herbal Oils: Herbal oils are effective for baldness, falling of hair, thinning of hair, in treating irritation & itching of scalp

vii) Herbal Perfumes & fragrances: Citrus Fragrance: The light, fresh character of citrus notes (bergamot, orange, lemon, petitgrain, mandarin etc.) is often combined with more feminine scents (flowers, fruits and chypre).

Herbal cosmetics have several advantages over synthetic ones

Figure 1: Advantages of herbal cosmetics

The most recent fashion and beauty trend is herbal cosmetics as shown in Table 1. Since natural products provide the body with nutrients, improve health, and provide satisfaction because they are free from synthetic chemicals and have considerably fewer side effects than synthetic cosmetics as shown in Figure 1, most women today choose natural products over chemicals for their personal care to enhance their beauty [5]. The following are a few benefits of utilizing natural cosmetics that make them preferable to synthetic ones:

Natural Products

By virtue of their name, herbal cosmetics are supposed to be all-natural and free of any potentially dangerous synthetic chemicals that could hurt the skin. These products use various plant parts and plant extracts in place of conventional synthetic products, such as Aloe vera gel and coconut oil. They also include natural nutrients like Vitamin E, which maintains healthy, radiant skin. For instance, Aloe vera, a kind of herbal plant in the Liliaceae family, is naturally occurring and accessible [6]. Consumers that want more natural products with traceable and natural ingredients, free of dangerous chemicals, and emphasizing the qualities of natural substances are becoming more and more prevalent. These consumers are concerned about ingredients such synthetic chemicals and mineral oils [7].

Useful and Safe

Natural cosmetics are safer to use than other cosmetics. They have been dermatologists-tested and dermatologist-proven hypoallergenic, making them safe to use anytime, anyplace. People don't have to worry about developing skin rashes or itching because they are made of natural substances. Examples include the synthetic antioxidants BHA (butylated hydroxyanisole) and BHT (butylated hydroxytoluene), which are used as preservatives in lipsticks and moisturizers [8]. BHA and BHT may cause adverse skin responses [9]. BHA is categorized by the International Agency for Research on Cancer as a potential human carcinogen [10]. Natural antioxidants like Vitamin C are present in herbal cosmetics [11].

Suitable for every skin type

All skin types can use natural cosmetics. Whether you have dark skin or are fair, you may discover natural cosmetics like foundation, eye shadow, and lipstick that work for you. They can be used by women with sensitive or oily skin without compromising their skin's state. The primary worry with particular coal tar colors (whether

created from coal tar or synthetically) is that they can cause cancer [12]. Coal tar is known to be a human carcinogen. Natural colors made from herbs, however, are safer.

Numerous options to pick from

Despite being a relatively new category in the cosmetics market, natural cosmetics already provide a wide range of beauty products for all make-up enthusiasts to choose from. A selection of naturally formulated foundation, eye shadow, lipstick, blush, mascara, concealer, and other beauty products are available. Additionally, natural cosmetics produced locally or by well-known international designers are available. Among the many different herbal extracts that are available are *Andrographis paniculata* (Kalmegh), *Asparagus racemosus* (Shatawari), *Boswellia serrata* (Salai Guggal) and Asphalt (Shilajit) [13].

In Your Price Range

Natural cosmetics don't cost a lot. In some cases, these goods are less expensive than synthetic ones. During sales, they are presented at a reduced price and are sold for a low cost. Just conduct enough research to hunt for excellent bargains. According to a WHO estimate, 80% of the world's population relies on natural goods for their healthcare due to the negative side effects and escalating costs of modern medicine. Due to their accessibility, affordability, and relative safety, traditional herbal remedies are today encouraged and recommended by the World Health Organization in natural health care programs [14].

No Side Effects

Synthetic cosmetics might irritate your skin and lead to breakouts. Your skin may become dry or oily as a result of them clogging your pores. One need not be concerned about them with natural cosmetics. The use of natural components ensures no negative effects; they can be used anywhere, at any time. For instance, herbal cosmetics are free of parabens, the most common preservative used in

cosmetics and a skin irritant [15]. and have endocrine disruption.

Regulation

A product's intended use determines whether it is considered a cosmetic or a drug for legal purposes. The line separating a cosmetic product from a medicine is not well defined under the current paradigm, and different rules and legislation are applicable to various product categories. A drug is defined as "all medicines for internal or external use of humans or animals" and "all substances intended for; or in the diagnosis, treatment, mitigation or prevention of any disease or disorder in humans or animals" by the drugs and cosmetics act of 1940. Cosmetics are defined as "any article intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, sprayed or applied to any part of the human body for cleansing, beautification, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance, and includes any article intended for use as a component of cosmetic." [16,17]. Some goods fall under both the criteria of cosmetics and medications. This might occur if a product has many intended uses. Fluoride-

containing toothpaste, deodorants that work as antiperspirants, and moisturizers with sun protection claims are a few examples of cosmetic/drug combos. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) review and approval process is required for claims made about medications, but it is not required for claims made regarding cosmetics. Although there isn't a specific legal category for cosmeceuticals, the term has come to be used to describe goods that fall in between cosmetics and pharmaceuticals [18,19].

Extracts for Herbal Cosmetics

Herbs are important, especially in modern times when the negative effects of overmedicating and food processing have reached alarming levels. As well as alternative medications, they are currently being used more and more in cosmetics, cuisines, and teas. Growing lifestyle modification efforts include the growing interest in herbs. This movement is founded on the idea that there is a great deal of promise for using plants as therapeutic agents (Figure 2) [20].

Aloe vera

Neem

Amla

Brahmi

Multani Mitts

Shikakai

Figure 2: Extracts for Herbal Cosmetics

Aloe vera (*Aloe barbadensis*)

It is a clever combination of an antibiotic, an astringent coagulating agent, a painkiller, and a growth stimulator (also known as a "wound hormone") that works to hasten the healing of wounds. It is applied both externally and internally and is used for sunburn relief, hemorrhoid healing, scratch treatment, and body or skin purging. It promotes the growth of new tissue and slows the progression of skin cancer brought on by the sun [20].

Neem (*Azadirachata indica*)

"Sarva Roga Nivarini: the curer of all ailments". As far back as 4500 years ago, neem was hailed as a miracle cure. Some of its health-improving advantages Effective in treating skin infections, rashes, and pimples, boosting immunity, combating obesity, purifying blood for glowing, healthy skin, preventing diabetes, fighting viruses, and getting rid of intestinal worms and parasites, malaria, piles, hair problems, and dental health issues [20].

Amla (*Emblica officinalis*) is the name given to the edible fruit produced by a little leafy tree (*Emblica officinalis*) that is native to India. The valuable oil that is collected from this fruit's seeds and pulp and used as a remedy for hair and scalp issues is in addition to its high vitamin C content one of its most treasured qualities. It is used for diseases in children, hair loss, and eye disorders, among other things [20].

Brahmi (*Bacopa monnoria*) The dried fruit of Reetha is used to make Reetha powder. It can be applied as a face pack to lighten the skin on the face. It is applied to the hair to make it shiny and to enhance its beauty. Additionally, it eliminates head lice and dandruff. Additionally, it can be used to wash wool clothing and clean jewelry. It is utilized in herbal shampoos and Ayurvedic preparations [20].

Multani Mitts (Fullers Earth) It is Mother Nature's own baby powder, one of the first

materials used as a beauty mask to pull oils from the skin, which are natural moisturizers for the hair, teeth, gums, and hair, was clay. removing acne scars, curing sunburn, clearing clogged pores, and cleaning the skin of dirt and flakes [20].

Shikakai (*Acasia concina*) In the hot, arid plains of central India, *Acasia concina* grows as a tiny shrub-like tree. The fruit of this tree, which resembles a pod, has been used for ages by those who have access to it to clean their hair. It is regarded as an excellent cleaner for "lustrous long hair" and has been said to "promote hair growth and prevent dandruff." Additionally, it aids in eradicating lice and dandruff and is quite effective in cleaning oil and debris out of hair [20].

Herbal Treatments for a Variety of Conditions

Treating dry skin

Aloe vera

This plant is indigenous to southern Africa and has thick, prickly leaves with yellow or red blossoms. Due to its ability to cure, moisturize, and soften skin, it is a common ingredient in cosmetic products. To quickly extract the calming gel, simply cut one Aloe vera leaf. Leucine, isoleucine, and saponin glycosides, which have cleaning properties, as well as the vitamins A, C, E, B, choline, B12, and folic acid, which have antioxidant properties, are all found in aloe vera.

Coconut oil

It is made by crushing the dried kernel, or copra, which contains between 60 and 65 percent oil. Lower chain fatty acid glycerides are abundant in coconut oil. Coconut oil is made from the fruit or seed of the *Arecaceae*-family coconut palm tree *Cocos nucifera*. Coconut oil has a melting point of 24 to 25 °C (75 to 76 °F), making it easy to use in liquid or solid form. It is frequently used in cooking and baking. Coconut oil does wonders to soften and moisturize the skin [21].

Jojoba oil

It is a blend of long-chain, linear liquid wax esters that is derived from the seeds of *Simmondsia*

chinensis, a desert shrub in the Simmondsiaceae family. Jojoba oil is frequently used in cosmetics as a moisturizer and as a carrier oil for exotic perfumes because it is simple to refine to remove any odor, color, and oxidative instability. Jojoba oil and human sebum are nearly equivalent. Sebum hydrates and protects the skin and hair, but it is removed by chemicals, pollutants, the sun, and aging, leading to dry skin and hair. Jojoba oil replenishes the nutrients that skin and hair lose while bringing them back to their ideal pH balance.

Olive oil

It is a fixed oil that is obtained from the fruits of the *Olea europaea* plant in the oleaceae family. Trilinolein, triolein, tripalmitin, tristearate, monosterate, triarachidin, squalene, -sitosterol, and tocopherol are the main components. In cosmetics like lotions, shampoos, and other products, it serves as a skin and hair conditioner. It is a strong promoter of fatty acid penetration [22].

Sunflower Oil

This is a non-volatile oil made from the seeds of *Helianthus annuus*, a member of the Asteraceae family. Lecithin, tocopherols, carotenoids, and waxes are all present in sunflower oil. It smoothes skin and is regarded as non-comedogenic [21]. Simple but affordable oil that has stood the test of time in a variety of emulsions designed for face and body goods [23].

Skin Protection

Green tea

The tea plant has been grown for a very long time in Asia [24]. Green tea is tea prepared only from *Camellia sinensis* leaves, a member of the Theaceae family [25]. Green tea leaves contain (2)-epicatechin (EC), EGC, (2)-EC-3-gallate, and EGCG, which is the four primary polyphenolic catechins contained in green tea leaves [26,27]. Green tea extracts most prevalent of the or a specific green tea polyphenol (GTPP), particularly epigallocatechin (EGC)-3-gallate (EGCG), were

found to inhibit two-stage chemical carcinogenesis, such as that caused by 7,12-dimethylbenz(a)anthracene [DMBA] and 12-O-tetra decanoylphorbol 13-acetate [TPA] as well as photo-carcinogenesis, which is brought on by UVB [28]. It is a top-notch skin protector. It limits inflammation and guards against direct cell damage. Green tea contains catechins, which have 20 times more antioxidant potential than even Vitamin E [25].

Calendula

Calendula officinalis is said to exhibit exceptional antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing properties [29]. According to a recent investigation, the primary constituents of the essential oil of calendula include -thujene, -pinene, 1,8-cineole, dihydrotageton, and t-murolol [30]. When used topically, calendula solution or tincture reduces inflammation, stops bleeding, and calms inflamed tissue while treating acne [25]. The use of calendula cream or ointment to treat radiation dermatitis is supported by "limited evidence" [31].

Turmeric

Hindus utilize turmeric in many of their festivities. Brides would apply turmeric on their bodies, especially in Hindu weddings, to give them a bright appearance. Babies are also given turmeric to rub on their foreheads for luck. For a naturally golden glow, women often apply turmeric on their cheeks [32]. The amount of UVB-induced sunburn cells in mice is decreased by this vivid yellow to orange powder [33].

Anti-aging Treatment

Carrot

Carrot is an anti-aging remedy that is derived from the Apiaceae plant species *Daucus carota*. Due to its abundance in Vitamin A and other necessary Vitamins, this herb has long been valued. As an anti-aging, reviving, and regenerating agent, carrot seed oil is utilized [21]. The carotenoids -carotene and smaller levels of -carotene and -carotene give the carrot its distinctive and vibrant orange color.

In people, and β -carotenes undergo a partial conversion to Vitamin A [34].

Ginkgo

The Ginkgoaceae family includes Ginkgo biloba. It is well recognized for acting as a circulatory tonic, namely for bolstering the minuscule capillaries that connect to all organs, but particularly the brain. As we become older (on average 32), the capillaries grow more flexible, allowing more oxygen to reach the brain and eyes (protecting against degenerative eye illnesses like macular degeneration). Ginkgo biloba (G. biloba) tree leaves and nuts have been used for thousands of years in China and Japan to treat a variety of illnesses, including impotence in men, poor blood circulation, hypertension, impaired memory, and depression in the elderly. It is also establishing a comparable reputation as an anti-inflammatory and antioxidant [35]. The flavone glycosides in the G. biloba extract EGb 761, which is made from the tree's leaves, are mostly derivatives of quercetin and kaempferol (33%), and terpenes (6%), which have demonstrated the ability to be isolated from the leaves of Lawsonia inermis and have demonstrated a significant antifungal antibiotic effect [36].

Rhodiola rosea

It is also known as Lignum rhodium, orpin rose, Aaron's rod, arctic root, king's crown, and golden root. It is a species of plant from the Crassulaceae family that lives in frigid climates. Traditional folk medicine used R. rosea to increase physical endurance, work productivity, longevity, resistance to high altitude sickness, and to treat fatigue, depression, anemia, impotence, gastrointestinal disorders, infections, and nervous system disorders [37]. It grows primarily in dry sandy ground at high altitudes in the arctic regions of Europe and Asia. Phenolic chemicals, which are known to have powerful antioxidant capabilities, are abundant in R. rosea [38].

Antioxidants

By scavenging free radicals or stimulating their disintegration and reducing such illnesses, antioxidants, whether synthetic or natural, can be useful in avoiding their production [39]. The use of herbal resources natural antioxidants is currently gaining popularity.

Tamarind

Tamarindus indica L., a member of the Fabaceae family and the Caesalpinioideae subfamily, is a fruit that contains minerals, amino acids, and fatty acids. The tartaric acid in tamarind gives it a sweet acidic flavor, which is its most distinctive feature. The tamarind fruit can be a significant food source because it is not only a rich source of carbohydrates but also a fantastic supply of vitamin B, minerals, and exhibits great antioxidant capacity that appears to be linked to a high phenolic content [40-44].

Vitamin C

Proline, procollagen, and lysine must be hydroxylated in order to function. The effects of photodamage can be improved by vitamin C. Some of the effects of photo-aging on skin have been reduced by using vitamin C to induce collagen repair.

Vitamin E

The primary lipophilic antioxidant in plasma membranes and tissues is vitamin E (alpha-tocopherol). 30 naturally occurring compounds (4 tocopherols and 4 tocotrienols) with vitamin E action are collectively referred to as vitamin E. By scavenging lipid peroxy radicals, it is thought to play a crucial role in halting chain propagation and lipid peroxidation and defending the cell membrane from oxidation [45].

Pomegranate

The pomegranate plant (Punica granatum) extract is thought to increase the effectiveness of topical sunscreens since it has antioxidant and antiviral qualities. It has been proven that pomegranate seed oil has chemopreventive properties against skin cancer. Pomegranate seed oil fractions and

pomegranate peel fractions may both promote dermal and epidermal regeneration, respectively.

Resveratrol

This polyphenolic phytoalexin substance is thought to be a potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-proliferative agent. It is found in the skin and seeds of grapes, berries, peanuts, and other foods. Skin cancer and other illnesses that are thought to be brought on by the sun have been targeted by resveratrol research.

When included in sunscreens, cosmetic lotions, and other skin care products, the antioxidant is proven to offer skin photoprotection. It is also

thought to work in concert with beta-carotene, vitamins C and E, and other nutrients.

Ferulic Acid

Ferulic acid (4-hydroxy-3-methoxycinnamic acid) is a powerful antioxidant that is used in sunscreens, cosmetic lotions, and other skin care products to protect skin from UV rays. Additionally, it is thought to work in concert with beta-carotene, vitamins C and E.

Liquorice

Glycyrrhiza glabra (G. glabra) extract has been used to treat dermatitis, eczema, pruritus, and cysts as well as skin irritation. Because of glycyrrhizin, it has a chemopreventive effect.

Table 1: List of Plants Used in Skin Care formulation.

Sr. No.	Plant name	Chemical constituents	Uses	References
1.	Badam <i>Prunus amygdalus</i>	3,-O-methylquercetin 3-O-β-d-glucopyranoside, naringenin 7-O-β-d- glucopyranoside, catechin, protocatechuic acid, vanillic acid, p- hydroxybenzoic acid	Kernel extract is used in sun creams formulations for skin fair and beautification creams	46
2.	Aaraar <i>(Juniperus communis)</i>	Monoterpene hydrocarbons, sabinene, α-pinene and limonene 44	Useful in skin creams to control skin rejuvenation	47,48
3.	Amla <i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Ellagitannins, emblicanin A, emblicanin B, punigluconin, pedunculagin, punicafolin phyllanemblinin A, phyllanemblin, ellagic acid, gallic acid	anti-oxidant properties	49,50
4.	Aswagandha <i>Withania somnifera</i>	Withanolides, (-)-sominolide, mindabeolide-1, withanolide-R, flabelline, corydaldine, Oxyhydrastine, fumaritine, protopine, fumariline, juziphine	skin cleansing formulations and possesses antioxidant properties	51,52
5.	Aam <i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mangiferin, isomangiferin, tannins, gallic acid, protocatechic acid, catechin, mangiferin, alanine, glycine, γ-aminobutyric acid, kinic acid, shikimic acid.	Anti-oxidants	53,54
6.	Chandan <i>Santalum album</i>	Alpha- and beta-santalol, cedrol, esters, aldehydes, phytosterols, squalene	Paste of hardwood is used in face pack; essential oil used in preparation of creams, ointments and lotions for skin beautification and protection from sunburn; possesses anti-oxidant properties	55-58

7.	Cucumber Peel <i>Cucumis sativus</i>	vitamins and minerals	Calm and cooling, Cucumber Peel extract makes a wonderful addition to skin care products for its toning and skin tightening properties	59
8.	Garlic <i>Allium sativum</i>	Llicin, phytoncidea, alliin, ajoene, isoalliin, methiin, alliin.	Garlic oil is useful to control sores, pimples and acne. It may be used in skin lotions and creams	60
9.	Haldi <i>Curcuma longa</i>	Curcumin, turmerone and zingiberene; cineole and p-tolylmethyl carbinol α -phellantrene, terpinolene, 1,8-cinceole, undecanol and p-cymene	Rhizome powder possesses anti-inflammatory and anti-oxidant properties; used in facial, face creams and ointments	61
10.	Karela <i>Momordica charantia</i>	Momordicin I, momordicin II, cucurbitacin B, momordin, charantin, charantosides, momordicinin,	antioxidant properties	62,63
11.	Lal gulab <i>Rosa damascena</i>	Citronellol, Citronellyl acetate, Citronellyl formate, eugenol, Farnesol, Geraniol, Nerol, Geranyl acetate, Geranyl formate, Linalool, Methyl isoeugenol, Rose oxide, Alpha-Terpineol, 4-Terpinenol, Methyl heptenone, Humulene, Hexanol, Guaiene, Eudesmol, Guaiene, Humulene	Essential oil extracted from flowers is used in skin creams, lotions and ointment for beautification, smoothness and protection from sunburns	64,65
12.	Lavender <i>Lavandula vera</i>	Resinous matter, tannic acid	Essential oil is used in skin anti-acne	66,67
13.	Neem <i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Di-n-propyl disulfide, 1-cinnamoylmelianolone, Isonimolicinolide, nimolicinoic acid	Bark, seed, fruits and leaves contain diterpenes and highly oxidized tetramer warmer parts triterpenoids including azadirachtin; antiseptic agent; useful in curing wounds, skin diseases, leprosy, ulcers	68
14.	Nariyal <i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Sugars, vitamins, minerals, amino acids and phytohormones	Coconut oil is useful for skin itching and rashes	69
15.	Nimbu <i>Citrus limon</i>	Limonene, β -myrcene and decanal	Potential source of vitamin C; oil is used in various preparation to reduce skin itching and skin nourishment, pulp left after extraction of juice is useful as a facial ingredient	70,71
16.	Papaya <i>Carica papaya</i>	Papain, chymopapain, carpain, carpasemine, benzyl isothiocyanate	Milky juice of unripe fruit is a good ingredient for facial and face cream; fruit pulps make skin soft and remove blemishes	72,73

17.	Til <i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Latifonin, momor-cerebroside, soya- cerebroside II, beta-sitosterol, daucosterol, D-galacitol	Seed extract is useful for skin protection and rejuvenation	74,75
18.	Akroot <i>Juglans regia</i>	Oleic acid, macadamia, linoleic acid, linolenic acid, methionine, cysteine, tryptophan, threonine	Leaves and hull of fruits is used for hair dyeing	76,77
19.	Water lettuce <i>Pistia stratiotes</i>	palmitic acids, anthocyanin-cynidin-3- glucoside, luteolin-7-glycosid, vitexin, orientin	Leaves extract is applied to control chronic skin disorders	78,79
20.	Sacha Inchi <i>Plukenetia volubilis</i>	Sacha Inchi Extract is rich in Omega 3 fatty acids. It also contains Omega 6 (linoleic) fatty acids and Vitamin A	helps to protect the skin from abuse of external elements, balances skin's oiliness, and locks in moisture to keep it well hydrated. It promotes elasticity which helps to keep your skin looking soft and supple	59
21.	Akash bel <i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	7'-(4'-hydroxy,3'-methoxyphenyl)-N- [(4-butylphenyl) ethyl] propenamide, 6,7-dimethoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2- one, 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-ethanoate, 2-(3-hydroxy-4- methoxyphenyl)-3	7'-(4'-hydroxy,3'-methoxyphenyl)-N- [(4-butylphenyl) ethyl]propenamide, 6,7-dimethoxy-2H-1-benzopyran-2- one, 3-(3,4-dihydroxyphenyl)-2- propen-1-ethanoate, 2-(3-hydroxy-4- methoxyphenyl)-3	47,48
22.	Tulsi <i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Eugenol, epi- α -cadinol, α -bergamotene, γ -cadinene	control skin infection and rejuvenation	80
23.	Lajwanti <i>Mimosa pudica</i>	Flavones, isorientin, orientin, isovitexin, vitexin	Herb extract applied in skin creams and lotions to control itching	81

CONCLUSION

Herbal cosmetics are created by starting with a base of cosmetic components, then adding one or more herbal elements to cure various skin conditions and enhance beauty. All of these cosmetic products have natural additives like waxes, oils with natural colors, natural perfumes, and plant components like leaves added to the chemical mix. Lipstick and rouge are examples of pure cosmetics, while antibiotics and corticosteroids are examples of pure pharmaceuticals. Cosmeceuticals are intermediary agents. The greatest way to lessen skin issues including hyperpigmentation, wrinkles, aging, and rough skin texture is to use cosmetic items. The market for herbal cosmetics is growing quickly.

Herbal cosmetics include benefits like lower prices, no side effects, environmental friendliness, user safety, etc. Compared to synthetic cosmetics, it has a fantastic future. An enormous and considerable expansion in the field of herbal cosmetics will result from proper control of these herbs and standardization.

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